

Proposed Marketing Strategy for Coffee Shop in Jakarta

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ABSTRACT: Most Indonesian people, especially the millennial generation, has adopted hanging out and drinking coffee into their way of life as a way to support their daily activities. coffee consumption hit 3,3 million bags @60kg, and the end of the year of 2021 it reached 5 millions of bags. Sicangkir Coffee is a coffee shop that placed in Pasar Minggu, South Jakarta which following the trend since 2018. After Pandemic covid-19 hit indonesia in 2020, sicangkir sales decline a lot and trying to regain the sales they used to have. Sicangkir have challenges due to proliferation of coffee shops in Jakarta.

Finding an appropriate marketing strategy to improve Sicangkir Coffee sales is the goal of this study. Internal and External analysis is carried out to understand business problem broadly and deeply. Analysis of the internal focus on STP (Segmenting, Targeting and Positioning) and Marketing Mix (7P), while the external analysis focus on PEST analysis, Porter Five Forces and Competitor Analysis. In this research both primary and secondary data were collected for analysis. All the analysis result are summarized in SWOT framework (Strengths, Weakness, Opportunitites and Threats) and further analyzed using TOWS matrix to generate several strategies proposals.

KEYWORDS: Brand Awareness, Coffee shops, Sicangkir Coffee, SWOT, TOWS.

INTRODUCTION

Most Indonesian people, especially the millennial generation, has adopted hanging out and drinking coffee into their way of life as a way to support their daily activities. (Elly, 2012). The phenomena of coffee shop are keep growing from a store only open in mall like starbucks and now we can see every street already having their own coffee shops, from café and the newest one is the coffee 2 go concept which only available for takeout. Coffee consumption for some indonesian people now becoming a needs or lifestyle. Coffee shops turn into the first thing to come in mind for spending time or hangout with friends. As shows in Figure 1, the trends in indonesia for coffee consumption are growing between 2010 and 2021. In 2010, coffee consumption hit 3,3 million bags @60kg, and the end of the year of 2021 it reached 5 million of bags, even with pandemic of Covid-19 the growth still high. It will also affect to the continously growing trend on the data for the upcoming year. Coffee shop trend also growing in line with the trend of coffee consumption becoming a very prospective business. Coffee consumption in indonesia not only from teenagers, but also from worker/businessman spend their time at coffee shop for discussing their business or meeting their client. The main thing that people do in coffee shop is only for relaxing or interact with other people. According to Arianto (2012), consumer attitudes and purchase decisions are influenced by lifestyle. According to Larasati (2013), customer happiness has an impact on a customer's loyalty. Loyalty will improve consumer interest in making purchases. Coffee shop is no longer business that providing food and beverages but now turn into creative business to attract their customer. Start from fast internet connection and aesthetic concept room which people can took photo and posted on social media, even a talkative barista now is a must so people who came to café will be entertained and back again just to enjoying the chit-chat. All those efforts are aimed for customer needs so they will satisfied after spending a quite big money for buying a coffee in good café. Customer not only came to coffee shop for all those facilities. In the end coffee shop is selling coffee, theres a lot of coffee shop which their target market is coffee addict. For consumer like this they only pay attention to the way of presentation, the quality of the coffee provided at a relatively cheaper price than a luxury coffee shop but still gives satisfaction to the taste of the coffee they enjoy.

Figure 1. Coffee Consumption in Indonesia 2010-2021
(Source: <https://dataindonesia.id>)

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Service Quality

By increasing customer satisfaction and dominating the competitive market, service quality is one of the essential strategies for maintaining prestige value. This makes it simpler for people to enter the market and gives businesses a tremendous chance to compete. In addition, many companies depend on the level of service they offer to their customers to stay in business (Taufik et al. 2021).

2. Product Quality

Kotler and Armstrong (2008:272) define product quality as the feature of a product that depends on its capacity to meet the expectations of customers, whether those needs are articulated or actualized. Schiffman and Kanuk (2007) defined product quality as a company's capacity to give each of its products a unique identity or trait that enables consumer recognition. The majority of products are offered at one of four quality levels: low quality, moderate quality, good quality, and very good quality, according to Kotler in Arumsari (2012:44). Several of these qualities can be quantified.

3. Competitive Price

Competitive pricing refers to a pricing approach where a business bases its prices on those of its competitors. By offering prices that are comparable to or lower than those of rivals while preserving profitability, competitive pricing aims to draw customers. Based on the notion that consumers are price-sensitive and will select the good or service that provides the most value for their money, the concept of competitive pricing was developed. Competitive pricing is a key tactic in the Indonesian consumer products sector, according to study by Gaffar and Sukarsono (2013). According to the survey, businesses who use competitive pricing are better equipped to compete in the market and keep their market share. Similar to this, Riasari (2017) discovered that competitive pricing is a successful strategy in Indonesia's fast-food restaurant sector, as price plays a significant role in customers' purchase decisions.

RESEARCH METHODS

Figure 2. Research Flow Design

This study starts with a look at business issues, where the author tries to look at the company both internally and externally. The author formulates the current difficulties to be exploited for research after researching and gathering enough information. The next stage is to gather the primary and secondary data necessary to aid in problem-solving. Then, in the following chapter, these data will be processed and examined appropriately so that they may present a comprehensive picture of the research findings and that the authors can then propose remedies that are anticipated to address the business problems of Sicangkir Coffee.

RESULTS

1. Segmenting, Targeting, and Positioning

The STP framework will help the author in determining the Sicangkir Coffee market's characteristics, potential targets, and positioning. By identifying the bases for market segmentation and creating consumer profiles according to their regional and demographic characteristics, market segmentation is meant. The following is a segmentation of Sicangkir Coffee:

Table 1. Segmentation of Sicangkir Coffee

Segmentation	Type of Segmentation	Description
Geographic	Country	Indonesia
	City	Jakarta
	Density	Urban
Demographic	Age	12 – 50 years old
	Gender	All Gender
	Education	Junior high school, High School, College
	Nationality	Indonesia
	Social Class	Low, Middle and Upper Class
	Occupation	Students, Employee, Entrepreneurs

Marketing targets are segments of the target market that have been carefully chosen by the business and consist of customers with similar requirements or characteristics. Sicangkir Coffee has chosen as its target market:

Table 2. Market Targeting of Sicangkir Coffee

Market Targetting	Description
Area	Around Jakarta Area
Age	15- 40 years old
Gender	All gender
Social Class	Low and Middle Class
Occupation	Students and Employees

Sicangkir Coffee aims to become a friendly place for millennials and their friends. Customers can also find a place to chill after a long day at work or to simply wait for Jakarta's traffic jam with reasonably prices coffee and food.

2. Marketing Mix (7P)

a. Product

The product offered by Sicangkir Coffee are coffee and non-coffee, the foods are coming from stand that join Sicangkir Place with profit sharing. The drinks menu that offered by Sicangkir Coffee as follows

Table 3. List of Drinks menus

Categories		
Manual Brew	Coffee	Non Cofee
Tubruk	Espresso	Tea
Pour Over (v60, Flat bottom, Wave)	Americano	Lemon Tea
Clever	Long Black	Lemon Tea Soda
Japanese Ice Coffee	Cappucino	Chocolate
Aeropress	Cafelatte	Choco Hazelnut
Vietnam Drip	Vanilla Latte	Choco Caramel
French Press	Hazelnut Latte	Fresh Milk
	Caramel Latte	Hazelnut Milk
	Mocchaccino	Caramel Milk
	Es Kopi Sicangkir	Green Tea
	Es Kopi susu Sicangkir	Thai Tea
	Es Kopi Soda Sicangkir	Taro
		Red Velvet
		Orange Squash
		Soda Susu
		Milky Fresh Yakult

Sicangkir Coffee that located near residence and school in Pasar Minggu affect the sales of product. As shown as in the table below, best selling product from Sicangkir Coffee is Es kopi susu Sicangkir, because its cheap and coffee latte with palm sugar is very popular these days. The second best is non coffee product, Milky Fresh yakult (orange) who slightly have more products sold than ice tea, because its also cheap and some of the customers who came to hangout at Sicangkir is a non coffee consumer.

Table 4. Sicangkir Product sold in Q4 2022

Menu	2022		
	October	November	December
Es Kopi Susu Sicangkir	815	840	983
Milky Fresh Yakult (orange)	175	170	192
Iced Tea	101	106	145
Iced Lemon Tea	87	91	102
Iced Americano	59	71	85

b. Price

Price that Sicangkir Coffee offered is a fixed price, it means the price has been calculated from the raw material, processes, then add product and service tax have been included. The price offered by Sicangkir Coffee is very affordable for coffee that based on Jakarta. The price range between Rp 13.000 – 23.000. here is the price menu for Sicangkir Coffee:

Table 5. List of Prices for Drinks menus

Category	Subcategories	Prices (IDR)
Manual Brew	Tubruk	18.000
	Pour Over	20.000
	Clever	20.000
	Japanese Ice Coffee	23.000
	Aeropress	23.000
	Vietnam Drip	23.000
	French Press	23.000
Coffee	Espresso	18.000
	Americano	20.000
	Long Black	20.000
	Cappucino	20.000
	Cafelatte	20.000
	Vanilla Latte	23.000
	Hazelnut Latte	23.000
	Caramel Latte	23.000
	Mocchaccino	23.000
	Es Kopi Sicangkir	20.000
Es Kopi susu Sicangkir	20.000	
Es Kopi Soda Sicangkir	20.000	
Non-Coffee	Tea	13.000
	Lemon Tea	18.000
	Lemon Tea Soda	23.000
	Chocolate	20.000
	Choco Hazelnut	23.000
	Choco Caramel	23.000
	Fresh Milk	18.000
	Hazelnut Milk	20.000
	Caramel Milk	20.000
	Green Tea	20.000
	Thai Tea	20.000

	Taro	20.000
	Red Velvet	20.000
	Orange Squash	20.000
	Soda Susu	20.000
	Milky Fresh Yakult (Orange, Strawberry)	20.000

Sicangkir Coffee doesn't want to compete in pricing with their competitors around them. Ziad as the owner give explanation about hangout places which customers come to order a cup of coffee and spend like 2-3 hours with it because the price usually bit high for a cup of coffee. Sicangkir wants to give an affordable price within Jakarta standart so people can reorder a coffee or tea while they are doing activities in Sicangkir.

Figure 3. Competitors Coffee prices
(Source: pergikuliner.com)

c. Place

Sicangkir Coffee located on Jl. Siaga Raya No. 42, RT.16/RW.3, Pejaten Barat, Ps. Minggu, Kota Jakarta Selatan, Daerah Khusus Ibukota Jakarta. The location of Sicangkir coffee is quite strategic because it's located in the main road and near residential area. There are many stores that until late night, so people don't need to worry if they are going back late.

Figure 4. Sicangkir Coffee location

d. Promotion

Figure 5. Sicangkir's Instagram

Sicangkir Coffee uses several promotional strategies. When it comes to Instagram they are not actively updating their feeds but everyday they use Instagram stories to remind their customer that the café is open. They do it constantly everyday with the same picture again and again without variation which will make consumers bored and can't attract more consumers.

Figure 6. Sicangkir Coffee instagram stories

Sicangkir Coffee instagram feeds also not active and for author is not that interesting enough to attract and convince people to buy the products. Sicangkir coffee last update on their feeds is on April 19th, 2022, which mean 1 year ago. There is no update on their feeds in 2023, only updating on stories everyday indicating open and close for online purchases without links for the services.

Figure 7. Sicangkir Coffee Instagram feeds

In Sicangkir Coffee instagram there are a link that connected to their online shopping method. There are 5 methods to do online shopping by GoFood, GrabFood, Grabfood by Ohaeri (food stall who join Sicangkir Coffee place), Tokopedia and Whatsapp. From 5 methods above, only 3 who active now there are GoFood, GrabFood and direct by whatsapp with mininum order. Ohaeri is no longer with Sicangkir since 2022 and Tokopedia which sell 1 ltr bottle is no longer active.

Figure 8. Sicangkir Coffee online services

After Pandemic Sicangkir try to make a special package for wedding, coffee stand or bottle for wedding bundling are available now. The wedding package doesn't update on instagram feeds, so people only know from offline store and word of mouth, but Sicangkit put stories highlight about wedding product in every wedding they attend.

Figure 9. Sicangkir Coffee Wedding Bottle

e. People

Because of the great impact that the employees have on Sicangkir Coffee's success, they are viewed as an essential component of the company. Currently, Sicangkir Coffee employs 4 baristas who occasionally double as waiters. Ziad, the owner, also occasionally works as a barista.

Figure 10. Sicangkir Coffee employee

To provide the highest quality service to the consumers, Sicangkir Coffee places a high value on the hiring and training of its employees. The barista has received training in making Sicangkir Coffee criteria, high-quality coffee. Ziad filters the staff, and in order for them to meet the standards of Sicangkir Coffee, they must be certified. Ziad is responsible for Sicangkir Coffee's menu quality control and research and development.

f. Physical Evidence

The physical environment is a condition that also include Sicangkir Coffee atmosphere, where the café services operate. With residential place close into the café, it makes Sicangkir a good place to hangout, people still active doing activities until 11pm which make Sicangkir safe situation.

Figure 11. Sicangkir Coffee Area

As shown as figure above, Sicangkir coffee area mostly outdoor and the indoor only for cashier and kitchen. Sicangkir Coffee area mainly focused for people hangout because there's a lot of tables and having very cozy atmosphere with spacious free parking lot. When customers came into Sicangkir they can see a beautiful concept so they can hangout for hours. Sicangkir also provide board games so customers can play with their friends.

g. Process

Begin with the consumer selecting a menu at the cashier, followed by placing an order and paying directly at the cashier with cash or an electronic wallet like OVO, Gopay, Qris, etc. The employee will then process the order following that. The customer can select a seat while they wait. The barista double-checks the drinks to ensure they are made according to Sicangkir Coffee standards. The barista will deliver the drink to the customer's table once all the stages have been completed. As of now, people can't do reservation at Sicangkir, which mean if the place is full, people need to wait until another table is empty.

3. PEST Analysis

a. Political Factors

These are all about how and to what degree a government intervenes in the economy. This can include - government policy, political stability or instability in overseas markets, foreign trade policy, tax policy, labour law, environmental law, trade restrictions and so on. The Ministry of Industry, represented by Putu Juli Ardika - Director General of Agro Industry, is targeting the opportunity for a political year beginning in 2023 to increase growth in the food and beverage industry, which is viewed as having the potential to continue to grow even though the pandemic period has not yet ended. The Ministry of Industry believes that the political year is inextricably linked to political parties, where consumption will increase (Junida, 2022). Previously, it was projected that the food and beverage industry would experience a growth rate of 3.57 percent in the third quarter of 2022, compared to 3.49 percent in the same quarter of the previous year (Kemenperin, 2022). Currently, government policies and politics are advantageous for the Indonesian coffee industry, as the government continues to facilitate business access in the coffee sector. To strengthen the resilience of the national economy, the government continues to encourage the economy through the National Economic Recovery (PEN) programme. One way it does this is by encouraging the performance and solid collaboration of national coffee industry stakeholders through the Indonesia Premium Coffee Expo & Forum 2022.

b. Economic Factors

Economic factors directly affect a market's or industry's profitability and general attractiveness. The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita is the most often used indicator of economic success for a national economy or a specific industry sector. This is commonly calculated using the Purchasing Power Parity (PPP) method to allow fair comparisons across other nations. The Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) at constant prices (real) can be used to display the overall annual rate of economic growth. A certain year is used to calculate GRDP at constant prices. The following graph demonstrates that DKI Jakarta, where Sicangkir Coffee is located, had an increase in economic growth overall. The value of the GRDP produced and the pace of economic growth are positively correlated in this circumstance. By being able to meet their consumption needs, one of which is coffee consumption, the population's wellbeing has increased as a result of the growth in the GRDP.

Figure 12. DKI Jakarta GRDP in 2016 – 2021
(Source: jakarta.bps.go.id)

c. Social Factors

Every activity that has a social impact on the market and community is considered by the sociological component (Rastogi & Trivedi, 2016). These elements, including demographics, cultural trends, and population analytics, among others (Yudha *et.al.*, 2018). Since drinking coffee has been established in Indonesian culture, it is anticipated that social elements will have a favorable influence on the growth of Sicangkir Coffee's business. This is evident from the coffee plantations that were started in the 16th century by the VOC, which can influence coffee consumption behavior and numerous terminologies, like *angkiran*, *kopi joss*, *kopi tubruk*, *kopi takar*, and serving coffee as a ritual custom, among others (Gumulya & Helmi, 2017). Indonesia will experience a demographic benefit in 2030–2040, when the number of people in the productive age group (aged 15–64 years) will outnumber those in the unproductive age group (aged under 15 and over 64). This demographic advantage can also help Sicangkir Coffee's business thrive (Harsono, 2019). Given that the population of productive age (aged 15–64 years) is Sicangkir Coffee's target market, it is projected that with this demographic bonus, growth in the Sicangkir Coffee industry will have more potential in the future.

d. Technology Factors

The rapid pace of technological change is driven through innovation, which is in turn created through entrepreneurs who seek to push boundaries of present limitations. Nowadays, a competitive advantage is short-lived because technology is growing rapidly. The use of information technology can provide benefits for companies related to communication, access to information, data management, and corporate decision making. When collaborating with parties outside the organization, technology can benefit businesses by decreasing expenses and enhancing access. Sicangkir Coffee employs information technology in the form of the internet and social media, particularly Instagram, to facilitate marketing and campaigning so that customers can quickly learn about the product. A summary of the results of the PEST analysis is shown in the following table.

Table 6. Summary of PEST Analysis results

Political	Economic	Social	Technology
Support from government Regulation (high)	Economic Growth (Medium)	Lifestyle Trends (High)	Internet and Social Media Culture (High)

4. Porter Five Forces Analysis

a. Rivalry among existing competitors

this force examines how intense the competition is in the marketplace. The quantity of current rivals and their individual capabilities are taken into account. When there are few companies selling a good or servicem when the market is expanding, and when customers may readily move to competitor’s product or service at little cost, there is a high level of rivalry competition. Competition between businesses can be fierce, which can lead to advertising dan price wars that can be harmful to a company’s bottom line. Jakarta has a large number of coffee shops, which increases the level of competitiveness in this industry. Many previously existing coffee shops offer high-quality coffee and services, and they already have loyal customers. There is a high demand for new coffee shops in urban areas like Jakarta because of the crowded and expanding society there. Based on the analysis, Author concludes that the rivalry among competitors is High

b. Bargaining power of suppliers

This force examines the amount of influence and control a supplier might have on the possibility of price increases, which would decrease a company's profitability. It evaluates the quantity of raw material suppliers and other resources that are offered. They have more influence the fewer suppliers there are. When there are many suppliers, businesses are in a better position. Since Sicangkir Coffee's food and beverage menus are commonplace in other coffee shops, the products presented can be characterized as being somewhat commonplace (non exceptional). so that Sicangkir Coffee can quickly find the ingredients for the cuisine and beverages supplied. Additionally, there are several alternatives to the suppliers as well as easy access to those who supply the raw materials for food and beverages. Author concludes that the supplier's bargaining power is low based on the analysis above.

c. Bargaining power of buyers

This force examines the power of the consumer, and their effect on pricing and quality. Consumers have power when they are fewer in number but there are plentiful sellers and it’s easy for consumers to switch. Conversely, buying power is low when consumers purchase products in small amounts and the seller’s product is very different from that of its competitors. Sicangkir Coffee is a coffee store, which is why the goods and services provided are those that are typical of a coffee shop. Because there are more coffee shops, customers may easily establish standards for the goods and services provided. Sicangkir Coffee's menu is comparatively similar to the menus presented at other coffee shops, which prevents the items from being distinguishable. Additionally, the growth of coffee shops may strengthen consumer bargaining power by allowing them to easily switch to competing products or brands at a lower cost. Considering the analysis above, author conclude that bargaining power of buyers is high.

d. Threat of new entrants

This force considers how simple or challenging it is for rivals to enter the market. The risk of a market share loss for an established business increases when new competitors find it simpler to enter the market. Absolute cost advantages, access to inputs, economies of scale, and strong brand identity are a few of the entry-level barriers. Sicangkir placed in Pasar Minggu area that quite expensive for renting a place to open business there, and the bare minum of opening coffee shop is quite high. Coffee machine for entry start at Rp 25.000.000 before any other equipment like glass, tables, etc. Because of those factors, this threat of new entrants of Sicangkir Kopi is low.

e. Threat of substitute products or services

The assumption that products or services that are offered from outside the specified industry may come close to satisfying present customers' wants is known as potential development of alternative items. Sicangkir Coffee sells

a variety of foods and drinks, with a focus on coffee menus and top-notch customer service. Sicangkir Coffee presents the idea of a coffee shop in this instance that is comparable to a café with a specialty on the coffee menu. There is a sizable possibility for the creation of replacement items in business models like Sicangkir Coffee. This can be seen in instances when rival restaurants or hotels have begun integrating the idea of a coffee shop into the scope of their operations. McDonalds and KFC (Kentucky Fried Chicken) are two fast food chains that have begun to open coffee shops inside of their establishments, with McDonald's using the McCafe concept and KFC using the KFC Coffee concept. Based on the analysis above, author conclude that threat of substitute product or services is high

A summary of the result of Porter’s Five Forces analysis is shown in the table below:

Table 7. Summary of Porter's Five Forces Analysis

Rivalry among competitors	Bargaining power of suppliers	Bargaining power of buyers	Threat of new entrants	Threat of substitute product or services
High	Low	High	Low	High

5. Competitor Analysis

A summary of the result of Competitors analysis is shown in the table below:

Table 1. Summary of Competitor Analysis

Marketing Mix	Sicangkir Coffee	Warunk WOW KWB	Resume Coffee
Product	Coffee, Non-Coffee, Finger foods.	Coffee, non-coffee, Indonesian foods, Ricebowl.	Coffee, Non-Coffee, Rice Box, Rice Bowl, Finger Foods
Price	Drinks: 13.000 - 23.000 Foods: 15.000 - 30.000	Drinks: 18.000 - 35.000 Foods: 10.000 - 42.000	Drinks: 15.000 - 29.000 Foods: 18.000 - 28.000
Place	Jl. Siaga Raya No. 42, RT.16/RW.3, Pejaten Bar., Ps. Minggu, Kota Jakarta Selatan, Daerah Khusus Ibukota Jakarta	Jl. Wr. Jati Timur Raya No.1B, RT.4/RW.3, Kalibata, Kec. Pancoran, Kota Jakarta Selatan, Daerah Khusus Ibukota Jakarta	Jl. Pejaten Barat Raya No.100, Ragunan, Ps. Minggu, Kota Jakarta Selatan, Daerah Khusus Ibukota Jakarta
Promotion	Instagram	Instagram, Tiktok, Youtube	Instagram
People	Less than 10 staff	More than 10 staff	Less than 10 staff
Process	Ordering is by reading/ scan the menu and doing the payment in the counter so the goods can be processed	Ordering is by reading/ scan the menu and doing the payment in the counter so the goods can be processed	Ordering is by reading/ scan the menu and doing the payment in the counter so the goods can be processed
Physical Evidence	Indoor & Outdoor seating, Smoking area, WIFI, comfort layout, Free parking space	Indoor & Outdoor seating, Smoking & non-smoking area, WIFI, comfort layout, big parking area	Indoor area & Outdoor area, WIFI, attractive design and layout

From the analysis of the competition can be seen that Warunk WOW KWB is the biggest threat. With high manpower and active in social media like instagram and tiktok. Warunk WOW KWB also using a media social specialist to make their marketing more advance with video on tiktok and instagram about event that will be held in Warunk WOW KWB, even

Resume Coffee also active in creating instagram content about coffee and videdo about how to buy coffee in Resume Coffee. For place, Sicangkir give spacious parking for car and bike while Resume Coffee doesn't have it, because in Jakarta parking space for hangout café is needed.

6. SWOT Analysis

After analyzing the internal and external factors, these are the SWOT analysis:

Table 2. SWOT Analysis

STRENGTH	WEAKNESS
(S1) Strategic place (S2) Good quality product (S3) Cheap product price (S4) Spacious parking place (S5) Variant of board games (S6) Good competency of employee	(W1) Didn't active on social media (W2) Lack of promotional effort (W3) Lack of employee
OPPORTUNITITES	THREAT
(O1) Coffee has become a trend in society. (O2) Growth of internet and media social users (O3) Demographic bonus	(T1) Growing number of competitors (T2) Threat for substitutes as places for hangout is also high.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In general, the external and internal conditions of Sicangkir Coffee are in decent condition. Sicangkir decline in term of doing online things and need some improvement in online marketing not only to cope up but to surpass their competitor in Jakarta, spesifically Pasar Minggu area to reclaim their profit before pandemic back.

The marketing strategies that Sicangkir Coffee need to apply based on the internal and external analysis are:

1. Sicangkir need to maximalizing their social media, not only as an "open-close" sign. Nowadays people are very close to social media, and they tend to find new places to hangout through social media. Even Sicangkir have a good coffee product with cheap prices it will be nothing if sicangkir can't be discovered by new potential customer.
2. Sicangkir need to hire a young media social specialist so they can cope up with trend nowadays so sicangkir able to attract new potential customer and retain existing customer.
3. Developing new product like canned coffee. Coffee is a lifestyle; people nowadays go everywhere grabbing their cup of coffee and posted it in their social media. The greater the design, people will attract to buy the product. Canned product not only will give a fresh look but give more durability and eco friendly rather than plastic.

Based on the proposed business solutions given in the previous chapter, author suggest improving their marketing way to gain new customer not only by word of mouth, but they also need much improvement on social media, following the trend nowadays. Try to update their instagram feeds atleast to show that sicangkir still exist in order to retain their existing customer. Quality of coffee and place of Sicangkir is already good but without a good marketing it will be a waste. Recruiting a young social media specialist will be a big leap for Sicangkir's brand in the future with an affordable price. Further research is still needed in the future era and technological development which will make some aaspect of this research irrelevant or need to be improvised.

As a recommendation, next researcher could collect more trustworthy data by enlisting a bigger number of respondents who could reflect the target market throughout Jakarta, possibly Java, or Indonesia. Therefore, with more innovation and technology, the coffee industry can grow in the future. Coffee used to be associated with drowsiness a few years ago, but today it's an item that people buy daily and everywhere, and this trend is expected to continue.

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